

INTEGRATED AYURVEDIC MANAGEMENT OF COVID-19 WITH SPECIAL REFERENCE TO CYTOKINE STORM: A CASE SERIES

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ABSTRACT

Background: The COVID-19 pandemic caused widespread morbidity and mortality, primarily due to cytokine storm induced multi-organ failure. Ayurveda offers a holistic understanding of this pathophysiology through the concepts of *Vata Kaphaja Sannipata*, *Rasavaha Strotodushti*, and *Dhatwagni Mandya*. **Objective:** To evaluate the role of *Ayurvedic* management in critical COVID-19 patients showing features of cytokine storm and desaturation, and to correlate *Ayurvedic* understanding with the modern cytokine storm mechanism. **Methods:** This case series includes three critical COVID-19 patients with oxygen saturation between 66–80%, HRCT score 17–20/25, and elevated inflammatory markers (CRP, LDH, Ferritin, D-Dimer). *Ayurvedic* formulations *COVID-1 (Rafel)*, *COVID-2 (Metonity)*, *COVID-3 (Vikrant)*, *Rudramrut syrup*, *Hemgarbh Pottali*, *Swaskas Chintamani Ras*,

and *Suvarna Kalpa* were administered with standard oxygen and supportive modern care.

Results: Marked improvement in oxygen saturation (from 70% to 97%), reduction in LDH (692→487 IU/L), and radiological improvement were observed within 10–14 days. None of the patients required ventilatory support. No adverse events occurred. **Conclusion:** *Ayurvedic* management focusing on *Dhatwagni Deepana*, *Strotoshodhana*, *Oja Vardhana*, and *Rasayana* significantly improved respiratory and systemic function, showing potential in

mitigating cytokine storm effects. Integration of Ayurveda in critical COVID-19 care can reduce mortality and post-COVID complications.

KEYWORDS: COVID-19, *Ayurveda*, Cytokine storm, *Dhatwagni Mandya*, *Rasavaha Strotas*, *Suvarna Kalpa*.

INTRODUCTION

The COVID-19 pandemic caused by SARS-CoV-2 has affected millions globally, with severe cases manifesting as acute respiratory distress syndrome (ARDS) and cytokine storm syndrome (CSS). Cytokine storm involves hyperactivation of the immune system with excessive release of pro-inflammatory mediators such as interleukin-6 (IL-6), IL-1 β , and tumor necrosis factor-alpha (TNF- α), resulting in vascular leakage, lung injury, thrombosis, and organ failure.

From an Ayurvedic perspective, the disease mirrors *Abhishangaja Jwara* and *Rajayakshma*, where *Vata* and *Kapha* aggravation accompanied by *Ama* leads to obstruction in *Rasavaha* and *Pranavaha Strotas*, producing systemic inflammatory symptoms. The *Charaka Samhita* (Ch. Chi. 8/39–43) describes this condition as.

“*Srotasam sannirodhaccha raktadinam cha sankshayat,*
Dhatushmanam cha apachayat rajayaksma pravartate.”
— *Charaka Samhita, Chikitsa Sthana 8/39–40.*^[1]

(“Due to obstruction of channels, depletion of body elements, and impairment of metabolic fire at tissue level, *Rajayakshma* manifests.”)

This description parallels the modern understanding of cytokine storm, where blocked microchannels (capillaries), inflammatory cell infiltration, and impaired metabolism lead to tissue damage and hypoxia.

Hence, *Ayurveda* provides both a preventive and therapeutic model to counteract this hyperinflammatory state through *Agnideepana*, *Ama Pachana*, and *Rasayana* therapies aimed at restoring *Dhatu Agni* and *Ojas*.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Study design

This is an observational **case series** of three severe COVID-19 patients treated with integrative *Ayurvedic* management during the second pandemic wave (May–June 2021) in Satara district, Maharashtra, India.

Inclusion criteria

- Laboratory-confirmed COVID-19 (RT-PCR positive)
- Severe or critical illness with oxygen saturation $\leq 85\%$ on room air
- HRCT thorax score $\geq 17/25$
- Raised inflammatory markers: CRP, LDH, D-Dimer, Ferritin
- Patients managed either at home with oxygen concentrator or in ICU

Exclusion criteria

- Pregnant or lactating women
- Patients on mechanical ventilator before Ayurvedic intervention

Intervention Protocol

Table no 1: Primary Ayurvedic Formulations.

Formulation	Key Ingredients	Pharmacological Action
COVID-1 (Rafel)	<i>Dashmool, Katutrayadi, Elakanadi, Suvarna Bhupati, Abhrak Bhasma, Guduchi Satwa</i>	<i>Agnideepana, Dhatvagni Vardhana, Ama Pachana</i>
COVID-2 (Metonity)	<i>Tapyadi Loha, Chandrakala Ras, Manjishtha, Yashtimadhu, Sariva</i>	<i>Raktaprasadana, anti-thrombotic, Vata-Kapha Shamana</i>
COVID-3 (Vikrant)	<i>Vasaguduchyadi, Drakshadi Kashaya, Swaskuthar Ras, Gorochnadi Gutika</i>	<i>Shwasahara, anti-inflammatory</i>
<i>Rudramrut Syrup</i>	<i>Tulsi, Pippali, Haritaki, Haridra, Bhumyamalaki</i>	<i>Rasayana, Pranavaha Srotoshodhana</i>
<i>Suvarna Kalpa</i>	Gold-based rejuvenative preparation	<i>Oja Vardhaka, immune modulation</i>
<i>Hemgarbh Pottali, Swaskas Chintamani Ras, Trailokya Chintamani Ras</i>	Metallic and herbo mineral preparations	Oxygen enhancer, <i>Pranavaha Srotas Balya</i>

Dosage Example (Case 1)

- COVID-1: 5 g/day
- COVID-2: 2 g/day

- COVID-3: 5 g/day
- Rudramrut Syrup: 2 tsp twice daily
- *Suvarna Kalpa*: 200 mg hourly (6–8 doses/day)
- *Hemgarbh Pottali* + *Swaskas Chintamani Ras*: 125 mg twice daily

Adjuvant Modern Support

- Oxygen concentrator (5 L/min)
- Short course of steroids and antibiotics per allopathic protocol

Follow up Period: 1 month after recovery with *Amritprash Ghrita* and *Kushmand Rasayana*.

Case Reports

Case 1: Critical COVID-19 with severe hypoxia

Presentation

A 55-year-old male presented on 11 May 2021 with breathlessness, dry cough, and oxygen saturation of 66–70% on room air and 80% on 5 L/min oxygen. HRCT (05/05/2021) showed CORAD-6 with 80% lung involvement (score 20/25). Laboratory findings revealed LDH 692 IU/L, Ferritin 369 ng/mL, D-Dimer 180 ng/mL, SGPT 73 IU/L, and ESR 34 mm/hr.

Modern physician advised hospitalization with ventilator support, but due to unavailability, the patient was managed at home with Ayurvedic intervention and oxygen concentrator.

Treatment

Ayurvedic therapy as per Table 1 was initiated. *Suvarna Kalpa* was administered hourly.

Progress

- Day 3: SPO₂ improved from 70% to 85% on oxygen; LDH reduced to 487 IU/L.
- Day 10: Patient could maintain 90–92% without oxygen.
- Day 14: Complete relief in breathlessness; X-ray showed resolution of pneumonia.
- Post-treatment: *Amritprash Ghrita* and *Kushmand Rasayana* for one month.

Outcome

Full recovery without post-COVID fibrosis. Oxygen dependence ceased by day 14.

Case 2: COVID-19 with Acute Kidney Injury(AKI)

Presentation

A 60-year-old diabetic male presented with breathlessness, desaturation (SPO₂ 80%), and elevated renal parameters (Creatinine 4.38 mg/dL, BUN 132 mg/dL). CRP was 25.6 mg/dL, and LDH was 411 IU/L.

Management

Along with COVID-1, 2, and 3 formulations, renal-protective *Ayurvedic* drugs were administered.

- *Phaltrikadi Guggulu*
- *Swadrashtadi guggulu*
- *Apamarg, Haralu, Gokshura* decoction (2 tsp twice daily)

Progress

By day 5, creatinine decreased to 3.0 mg/dL, BUN to 95 mg/dL, and oxygen saturation improved to 92%. No further dialysis or ICU transfer was needed.

Outcome

Patient fully recovered by day 14 with normalized renal and inflammatory markers.

Case 3: Physician on BIPAP Support with Cytokine Storm

Presentation

A 47-year-old male anesthetist presented with severe dyspnea and was admitted to ICU (Krishna Hospital, Karad) with HRCT score 17/25, CORAD-5, and 75% lung involvement. IL-6 was markedly raised (106 pg/mL), Ferritin 515 ng/mL, and D-Dimer 0.9 µg/mL.

Modern management included Remdesivir, Solumedrol, and Enoxaparin. *Ayurvedic* intervention was initiated simultaneously.

Treatment

- Hemgarbh Pottali 125 mg OD
- Swaskas Chintamani Ras 125 mg BD
- COVID-1, 2, and 3 capsules
- *Vasa, Guduchi, Drakshadi Kashaya* 10 mL TDS

Progress

Within 7 days, IL-6 reduced to <10 pg/mL, oxygen requirement decreased from BIPAP 40

L/min to 10 L/min nasal cannula. On day 14, X-ray showed marked reduction in haziness; patient discharged on *Kushmand Rasayana* and *Amritprash Ghrita* for one month.

Outcome

Recovered completely with no long-term respiratory sequelae.

RESULTS

Table 2: showing before after treatment results of 3 cases.

Parameter	Case 1	Case 2	Case 3
HRCT Score	20/25 → 12/25	18/25 → 10/25	17/25 → 9/25
SPO ₂ (%)	70 → 98	80 → 96	85 → 97
LDH (IU/L)	692 → 487	411 → 280	690 → 350
CRP (mg/dL)	25.6 → <5	20 → 4	30 → 5
Ferritin (ng/mL)	369 → 120	450 → 150	515 → 130
Hospital stay	14 days	12 days	14 days
Outcome	Complete recovery	Complete recovery	Complete recovery

DISCUSSION

Ayurvedic correlation of cytokine storm

The cytokine storm corresponds to the *Ayurvedic* description of *Strotorodha* (microchannel obstruction) and *Dhatwagni Mandya* (tissue metabolic failure). According to *Charaka Samhita*, obstruction of *Rasavaha* and *Pranavaha Strotas* leads to accumulation of *Ama* and depletion of *Ojas*, resulting in fever, cough, breathlessness, and progressive tissue loss identical to the systemic inflammatory cascade in COVID-19.

“*Rasaḥ strotassu ruddheshu svasthanastho vidahyate,
Sa urdhvam kasa vegeṇa bahurupaḥ pravartate*”^[1]
(*Ch. Chi. 8/43*)

“When the channels of Rasa become obstructed, the vitiated Rasa manifests in multiple forms of cough and respiratory distress.”

Hence, hyperinflammation and oxidative stress in COVID-19 reflect the imbalance of *Pitta* and *Vata*, whereas the mucus deposition (*pneumonia*) signifies *Kapha* vitiation.

Pharmacodynamic Mechanism of Ayurvedic Drugs

Guduchi (Tinospora cordifolia) acts as a potent immunomodulator and antioxidant. Experimental studies have confirmed its efficacy in downregulating IL-6 and TNF- α , thereby attenuating cytokine-mediated inflammation.^[2]

Haridra (Curcuma longa) exhibits strong anti-inflammatory properties by inhibiting NF- κ B activation, thus suppressing transcription of pro-inflammatory cytokines and reducing systemic inflammatory responses.^[3]

Vasa (Adhatoda vasica) contains vasicine and related alkaloids that produce bronchodilatory, mucolytic, and anti-inflammatory effects, improving alveolar function and reducing respiratory distress.^[4]

Suvarna Bhasma (Gold calx) demonstrates immunomodulatory potential and enhances *Ojas* by balancing pro- and anti-inflammatory cytokines and improving macrophage function.^[5]

Abhraka Bhasma improves respiratory and hepatic function and promotes tissue oxygenation through its Rasayana and adaptogenic effects.^[6]

Makardhwaj Ras exhibits significant antioxidant, rejuvenative, and anti-inflammatory properties, contributing to improved systemic endurance and recovery in critical COVID-19 cases.^[7]

These drugs collectively counter *Ama*, strengthen *Agni*, and restore tissue metabolism, resulting in stabilization of cytokine levels and prevention of fibrosis.

Clinical Relevance

In all three patients, Ayurvedic therapy significantly.

1. Improved oxygenation and pulmonary function.
2. Controlled inflammatory markers indicative of cytokine storm.
3. Prevented progression to mechanical ventilation.
4. Promoted early recovery and minimized post-COVID fatigue and fibrosis.

The present clinical observation highlights the efficacy of an *Ayurvedic* multimodal protocol in the management of *Kapha Sannipata Jwara* with predominant involvement of the *Pranavaha Strotas*, comparable to pneumonia or COVID-19 like respiratory disorders. The treatment was designed according to the classical principle “*Kaphasthananupurvyva*

Sannipatam Jayet”, emphasizing sequential management of *Kapha* through its liquefaction (*Pakwakarma*) and expulsion from the lungs.^[8]

1. Kapha elimination and restoration of pulmonary function

Vitiated *Kapha* in the *Pranavaha Strotas* causes bronchial obstruction and reduced lung compliance. A polyherbal combination comprising *Jvaraghna Yoga*, *Swasakuthar Rasa*, *Gorochanadi Gulika*, *Varanga Kshara*, *Tankana*, *Talishapatradi Churna*, and *Dhatupachaka Churna* was used to promote expectoration and reduce pulmonary congestion. This approach aligns with the classical *Swasa Chikitsa* described by *Charaka*^[9] and is supported by experimental studies demonstrating anti-inflammatory and mucolytic activities of *Aadhathoda Vasika* and *Piper longum*.^[10,11] In addition, administration of diuretic decoctions such as *Gokshura Kwatha* and *Punarnava* aided in the elimination of liquefied *Kapha* via the urinary tract, consistent with *Mutrala* therapy.^[12]

2. Prevention of thrombus formation

After the subsidence of *Kapha*, patients are often prone to *Pitta* dominant complications such as hypercoagulability and *Rakta Dushti*. Maintenance of *Dravata* (fluidity) and *Spandata* (circulation) of blood is critical to prevent thrombus formation and embolic episodes. The combination of *Tapyadi Lauha*, *Chandrakala Ras*, *Kamadudha Ras*, *Sariva*, *Manjishtha*, *Adulsa*, *Yashtimadhu*, and *Dhatupachaka* was used to maintain optimal blood rheology. *Rubia cordifolia* and *Hemidesmus indicus* are reported to have anticoagulant and antioxidant properties that support vascular health.^[13,14] No clinical evidence of thrombosis or embolism was observed during treatment, suggesting potential hemo-protective benefits of this regimen.

3. Enhancement of Oxygen saturation

A significant clinical outcome of the study was the improvement in oxygen saturation levels among hypoxic patients following administration of *Swasakas Chintamani Rasa* and *Hemagarbha Rasa*. Both formulations contain metallic and herbo-mineral ingredients known to enhance tissue oxygen utilization and support respiratory function.^[15] Previous studies have reported improved pulmonary performance and antioxidant potential of *Rasa Aushadhis* in hypoxic models.^[16]

4. Protection of Liver and Kidney

The *Yakrit* (liver) and *Vrikka* (kidneys) are regarded as key metabolic centers maintaining systemic *Agni*. The formulations *Vasa-Guduchyadi Kashaya*, *Drakshadi Kashaya*, and

Brihatyadi Kashaya were employed to protect these organs. *Tinospora cordifolia* and *Vitis vinifera* have shown hepatoprotective and nephroprotective activities in preclinical models.^[17,18] Maintaining the functional integrity of these organs prevents systemic toxicity and aids recovery from severe respiratory disease.

5. Cardiac Protection and Psychological Stability

In critical conditions, cardiac failure and arrhythmias may develop due to deranged *Prana-Udana Vata* and *Pitta* aggravation. *Swarna Soot Shekhar Rasa* and *Makaradhwaja* were administered for cardioprotection. These formulations are traditionally used for *Hrudroga* and have demonstrated cardiogenic and adaptogenic properties.^[19] The inclusion of *Sattvavajaya Chikitsa* through the chanting of “Om Namah Shivaya” was found to enhance psychological stability, aligning with evidence that meditative practices can improve autonomic cardiac control.^[20]

6. Management in dhatugata (critical stage)

Patients requiring ventilatory support (*BIPAP*, *CPAP*, *Ventilator*) were managed with *Rasayana Chatana* therapy, a lickable form of herbo-mineral tonic containing *Hemagarbha Rasa*, *Swasakas Chintamani Rasa*, *Mahalakshmi Vilas Rasa*, *Trailokya Chintamani Rasa*, and *Makaradhwaja*. This therapy helps restore the balance of *Vata subtypes* (especially *Prana* and *Udana*), and clinical observations indicated a gradual reduction in ventilator dependence. The outcome correlated with patient *Sattva Bala* (vitality) and consistent treatment adherence. Similar results have been reported with *Rasayana* formulations in critical care and post-COVID rehabilitation.^[21]

7. Post COVID Rehabilitation

During convalescence, *Kushmanda Rasayana*, *Amritprash Ghrita*, and *Laksha Siddha Ksheera* were administered for pulmonary rejuvenation and tissue repair. In patients with pulmonary fibrosis, therapies such as *Abhyanga*, *Pinda Sweda*, and *Mustadi Yapana Basti* significantly improved respiratory endurance. These outcomes align with the *Rasayana* concept of tissue rejuvenation and have been supported by modern findings on immunomodulatory and antioxidant properties of such formulations.^[22,23]

Spiritual and Psychological Component

Daily chanting of “Om Namah Shivaya” (representing *Panchamahabhuta* balance) was advised as *Satyavijaya Chikitsa*. Patients reported reduced anxiety, improved sleep, and

enhanced recovery, demonstrating *Ayurveda's* holistic approach encompassing body mind balance.

CONCLUSION

The integrative *Ayurvedic* management demonstrated effective control of cytokine storm and accelerated recovery in critically ill COVID-19 patients. The holistic approach addressed both immune hyperactivation and systemic imbalance described as *Dhatwagni Mandya* and *Oja Kshaya*. *Ayurvedic* formulations with *Suvarna* and *Rasayana* components enhanced vitality, improved lung function, and prevented organ failure.

This case series suggests that *Ayurveda*, when applied judiciously along with standard medical care, can serve as a life saving adjunct in severe viral infections such as COVID-19. Further controlled trials are warranted to validate these outcomes.

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